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FOOD SECURITY ISSUES IN UZBEKISTAN.

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to modern problems of food security in the world and its features in the country. The article also highlights the scope of work on food security in Uzbekistan based on practical analysis and presents relevant conclusions and recommendations.

Introduction: Ensuring food security is the key to Uzbekistan's independence and socio-economic and political stability in the country. Natural disasters, water shortages for irrigation, and droughts as a result of climate change are making it difficult to produce food. As a result, prices in world food markets are rising. The global financial and economic crisis that began in 2008 and continues to this day is exacerbating this problem. This is clearly evidenced by the fact that families in 54 countries around the world have experienced a decline in their financial well-being, the majority of the population in more than 20 countries suffers from hunger, and the average life expectancy of the population has decreased in 12 countries. In recent years, more than 840 million people in the world have suffered from hunger [1]. That is why great importance is attached to ensuring food security throughout the world.

Since the early years of independence, food security issues have occupied one of the central places in the socio-economic policy of Uzbekistan. Now the issues of further improving the well-being and quality of life of the population, ensuring the full supply of food to the population are closely related to the problem of ensuring food security. Therefore, the need to study the theoretical foundations and priority areas of ensuring food security on the basis of the implementation of the food program in Uzbekistan from a scientific and practical perspective has determined the relevance of this research topic.

Analysis of relevant literature:

In order to solve the theoretical and practical issues of food security as an integral part of economic security and justify its role in the development of society and the well-being of humanity, D.V. Zerakalov, an economist from various CIS countries, in his monograph "Food Security" presents a number of practical analyses of food security issues in world historical processes.

Ensuring food security is a global economic problem that will become a global economic problem by the 21st century, and many official statistical materials are analyzed[3]. Another economist, L. Revenko, in his official article "Food Security: Is There a Way to Find a Solution," raises the issue of ensuring food security on the world stage, mainly through external flows, that is, by distributing it depending on the production potential and capabilities of countries[4]. Some aspects of the problem being studied in Uzbekistan are generally studied in the textbook "Economic Security of the State" by H.P. Abulkasimov, while another of our economists, N.Kh. Ergashev, shows the importance of insurance in ensuring food security in Uzbekistan[5].

Also, some aspects of the issue of food security have been studied in their textbooks and textbooks by our country's economists Sh. Shodmonov, A. Ulmasov, T. Juraev, D. Tojibaeva. It should be noted that although the studies conducted by foreign scientists used many years of official data, they did not provide practical recommendations and proposals for their implementation within the national economy. The studies examined mainly considered the issue of food security as a factor that creates global economic security.

Research methodology:

The research was conducted to improve the theoretical and practical aspects of food security issues, and clear priority tasks were identified. In writing the article, an attempt was made to reveal the problem using methods such as analysis and logic, and a practical analysis of agricultural acreage and products, which are among the leading sectors in ensuring food security in Uzbekistan, was provided. The information necessary for the study was mainly obtained from foreign literature, statistical and regulatory databases.

Analysis and results:

With the country's population growing and urbanization processes intensifying, the reduction of agricultural acreage is increasingly making it more difficult to expand the possibilities for food production and meeting the needs of the population. According to a study conducted by the US Research Center, Uzbekistan ranked 64th in the world in the food security rating[6]. In our country, the land area used for agriculture increased from 28,080.4 thousand hectares in 1990 to 25,621.6 thousand hectares in 2015, i.e. -2,458.8 thousand hectares, correspondingly, the arable land area increased from 4,176.5 thousand hectares to 4,043.6 thousand hectares, i.e. -132.9 thousand hectares, irrigated land - 3,407.3 thousand hectares to 3,288.2 thousand hectares, i.e. -119.1 thousand hectares, and agricultural arable land decreased from 4,200.1 thousand hectares to 3,694.2 thousand hectares, i.e. -505.9 thousand hectares [6]. This indicates that ensuring food safety is of urgent importance. It should be said that the statistical studies conducted in 1989, when the former Union was in decline according to data, interruptions in the consumer market for about 95% of all products needed by the population and this led to the introduction of the system of selling basic daily food products to the population through cards in the territory of the former Union. In 1989, 89.3 percent of those who took part in the official surveys conducted by the republic's statistical authorities among the population of our country said that they do not consume enough meat products. These indicators were 56.5 percent for dairy products, 55.3 percent for sugar, 49.5 percent for confectionery products, and 17.5 percent for potatoes[7].

These figures show that on the threshold of independence, there were strong threats to food security in our republic, that the republic was no longer capable of ensuring food security. Hence food security after independence became a matter of life and death.

□ creating and improving the legal, legal and regulatory framework for ensuring food security;

- encouraging the development of food production through budget and tax funds. This includes the provision of tax incentives, subsidies and subventions;

- encouraging food production through monetary and credit policy instruments. This includes the introduction of a preferential lending system;

- regulating food exports and imports with and without customs tariffs. This includes measures to regulate and encourage the import of food products that are not produced in the country or are produced in small quantities, as well as the export of food products, including agricultural food products, by local producers, with and without customs tariffs;

- encouraging investments in the sectors of the agro-industrial complex (AIC). Measures will be taken to encourage domestic and foreign investments in the branches of the agro-industrial complex, including agriculture and fisheries, water industry, and food industry, to establish free agrarian economic zones, agricultural clusters in the country's regions, and to develop a favorable business environment for their development.

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6. <https://daryo.uz/k/2018/04/30/ozbekiston-oziq-ovqat-xavfsizligi-reytingidadunyoda-64-orinni-egalladi>Uzbekistan ranked 64th in the world in the food security rating